
The Role of Efficient Algorithms in Optimizing Computer Resource and Energy Use

**Developing Green GIS Technology for High-Precision
Cadastral GIS, Renewable Energy, LiDAR & Remote Sensing,
Telecommunications: Advancing Accuracy, Legal Integrity,
and Environmental Sustainability**

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The Role of Efficient Algorithms in Optimizing Computer Resource and Energy Use: Developing Green GIS Technology for High-Precision Cadastral GIS, Renewable Energy, LiDAR & Remote Sensing, Telecommunications: Advancing Accuracy, Legal Integrity, and Environmental Sustainability

Efficient algorithms play a crucial role in how computer resources are used, particularly in terms of energy consumption.

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Preamble

Digital technology is revolutionizing and reshaping our world, impacting economies on a global scale. Businesses across all sectors are integrating digital technologies to enhance their functionality and efficiency. This transformation extends beyond engineering, production, and service delivery; it encompasses entire sectors such as energy, land use, and even government operations. Embracing digital solutions has become a strategic approach for achieving sustainable growth. Digital technologies are changing the way businesses manage operations, conduct research, produce goods, and serve customers. They streamline internal processes and redefine how businesses interact within their ecosystems and comply with regulatory frameworks.

In the digital world, we constantly hear about algorithms in developing digital solutions. The efficiency brought by algorithms in problem-solving is a pivotal factor in enhancing productivity across numerous fields. The right algorithm can simplify complex problems, requiring minimal resources and time—a crucial advantage in today's fast-paced world. Our research underscores how algorithms boost efficiency by optimizing resource use, whether by reducing the memory or processing power needed for computational tasks. Beyond computational benefits, the right algorithm can drastically cut the time needed to find solutions, underscoring the critical role of time in achieving success.

However, the technological advancements driven by algorithms are underpinned by continuous development. Our research highlights the necessity of refining algorithms and practices to foster green software development. This approach not only drives innovation in IT but also contributes to a sustainable future. Examples from GIS and LIDAR technology illustrate the significant potential for achieving environmental goals while enhancing efficiency.

Intro

With digital technologies deeply integrated into every aspect of our lives, we must now focus on a bigger goal: adopting environmentally responsible technologies and practices to mitigate the environmental impact across the entire lifecycle of IT products and services.

At its core, Green IT is all about sustainability, aligning cutting-edge technology with environmental stewardship. It emphasizes the adoption of eco-friendly practices throughout the entire IT lifecycle, ensuring that businesses can thrive, while also protecting the planet. This approach benefits the environment, and enhances businesses's efficiency and reputation.

Green IT initiatives

To understand modern Green IT initiatives, we must first look back to their origins. In the 1990s, Europe and the United States spearheaded efforts to embed environmental responsibility into the tech sector. Despite these early initiatives, CO2 emissions have alarmingly increased since then, predating even the turn of the century. This historical perspective underscores the ongoing need for robust, eco-friendly technology practices today.

Fig.1 Global CO2 emissions from energy combustion and industrial processes, 1900 - 2022
IEA (2023), *Global CO2 emissions from energy combustion and industrial processes, 1900-2022*, IEA, Paris <https://www.iea.org/data-and-statistics/charts/global-co2-emissions-from-energy-combustion-and-industrial-processes-1900-2022>, Licence: CC BY 4.0
Image Source: <https://www.iea.org/data-and-statistics/charts/global-co2-emissions-from-energy-combustion-and-industrial-processes-1900-2022> ; IEA. Licence: CC BY 4.0

Patterns of Use, and Environmental Impact in the IT Sector:

The Center for Sustainable Systems, University of Michigan has stated that, in 2019, an astounding 2.16 billion mobile phones, tablets, and PCs were sold globally. Just a decade earlier, in 2010, the global sale of smartphones was at 297 million, a figure that surged to over 1.4 billion by 2021. This explosion in device usage is underscored by the fact that ‘more people worldwide now have mobile phones than access to safe sanitation’¹.

In North Macedonia, the digital landscape among enterprises shows significant integration of computers and internet access. The following statistics provide an overview of the current state:

Information and Communication Technologies in the Enterprises according to the number of employees, 2023				
	Enterprises according to the number of employees			Total
	(10-49)	(50-249)	(250+)	%
Enterprises with computer	96.1	97.9	98.8	96.4
Enterprises with internet access	95.9	97.9	98.8	96.2

Fig.2 Data source: https://www.stat.gov.mk/pdf/2023/8.1.23.30_mk.pdf ; © Republic of North Macedonia State Statistical Office

Key Indicators

Businesses With 10 or More Employees Having Internet Access

Time series for:

2023	96.2	%
2022	95.1	%
2021	94.1	%
2020	96.9	%
2019	95.6	%
2018	92.4	%
2017	92.4	%
2016	93.8	%
2015	93.5	%
2014	93	%
2013	92	%
2012	88	%
2011	88.6	%

Fig.3 Data source: <https://www.stat.gov.mk/IndikatorITS.aspx?id=27> ; © Republic of North Macedonia State Statistical Office

Taking all of the above mentioned into account, with the ‘newly’ popular advancements in machine learning, this does translate into significant environmental implications within the realm of Green IT.

1) Data Source –The Center for Sustainable Systems, University of Michigan:
<https://css.umich.edu/publications/factsheets/built-environment/green-it-factsheet>

Training machine learning models, particularly Large Language Models (LLMs) with hundreds of billions of parameters, among various different uses, requires substantial computational resources, energy, and materials (*Virtus Lab.*,(n.d.)). These models demand millions of GPU hours, which in turn contribute to increased carbon emissions. As we push the boundaries of artificial intelligence, it's crucial to address and mitigate the environmental impact associated with these powerful technologies².

The environmental impact of all this is clear, urging us to scrutinize the broader implications of existing technologies. **Understanding these impacts is essential for promoting a sustainable future through Green IT.**

We are aware, and we've witnessed a rise in CO2 emissions since 1990, and we're also aware of the environmental footprint of AI models, which have become popular and indispensable. So, let's explore how software, data centers, and algorithmic efficiency contribute to the global environmental footprint of technology.

Software's Role in Data Centers:

Software design is crucial in determining energy consumption, highlighting the interdependent relationship between software and data centers, the backbone of our technological infrastructure.

The efficiency of data centers hinges on the software systems managing data. Advanced software solutions, such as virtualization and workload optimization, significantly influence energy consumption within these centers.

And, naturally, measuring the actual power usage of both software and cloud services is complex.

SGIS Technology Initiative

The Genesis of SGIS Technology and Products

This research explores the vital role of energy-efficient algorithms in optimizing how computers consume resources, emphasizing their significance in advancing technology while promoting sustainability.

When it comes to GIS technology and projects, we often deal with vast amounts of data—commonly referred to as big data. Big data is characterized by its volume, velocity, and variety, meaning large quantities of data are generated quickly and come in various formats (Big data and GIS, n.d.). Although GIS data and big data are not identical, they are closely related and frequently integrated. When combined, GIS and big data offer powerful insights into a multitude of real-world challenges. Examples of big data sources include satellite images and extensive graphical data containing complex attributes and metadata.

2) *Data source: Impact on Machine Learning on Green IT initiatives <https://virtuslab.com/blog/business-insights/what-is-green-it/#impact-of-machine-learning-on-green-it-initiatives>*

The rise of big data has revolutionized every industry - GIS is no exception. This shift has significantly changed how we acquire and use spatial information. Organizations are increasingly using geographic information science and technology. While government agencies were historically the main users of geospatial data, today, businesses across all sectors are adopting GIS at a rapid pace.

The most critical aspect of developing GIS technology is ensuring it can effectively manage these types of big data. This capability is fundamental to the success and efficiency of any GIS project.

Algorithm Efficiency and Resource Optimization

Traditionally, we measure algorithm efficiency by how well it solves problems and how much computing power and storage it requires.

But with energy becoming a costly and limited resource, there's a new focus on the environmental footprint of algorithms. This shift reflects a broader awareness of energy's importance and prompts us to rethink how algorithms are designed and used.

Let's first explore how well available open-source GIS software handles running procedures and solves real-world problems. Several software packages have been tested for the purpose of this research;

Evaluation of open-source GIS software and the resources required for smooth operation of user procedures;

1. System Requirements for Using QGIS

Recommended Computer Settings

Before installing QGIS on a personal computer, the user must ensure that the computer meets the necessary requirements to run the program (Illinois Drainage Guide & American Society of Overseas Research, 2022). Inadequate hardware can cause the user's GIS software to stall or crash when processing large datasets. The primary considerations are:

1. RAM – 8GB of RAM or higher is recommended for using QGIS and avoiding system crashes.
2. CPU Speed – Higher than 1.9 GHz is recommended, although not required. QGIS might run slow at lower levels.
3. Hard Drive Storage – This is dependent on every individual dataset, but 1GB or more of storage would provide ample space.

System Components	Minimum	Recommended
Processor (CPU)	Core i3 2.7 GHz	Core i7 3.5 GHz
Memory (RAM)	2 GB	8 GB or more
Hard Disk	500 GB SATA	128 GB SSD or 500 GB SATA
Graphic Card	1 GB RAM	2 GB RAM (NVIDIA GeForce)
Operating System	Windows 7-10, macOS, Linux, BSD, and various Android apps for mobile and tablets	Windows 7-10, macOS, Linux, BSD, and various Android apps for mobile and tablets

Note: QGIS is a resource-intensive software. When in use, it does not like sharing the system's memory with other applications. It is recommended to close any unnecessary memory-consuming applications running in the background to ensure optimal performance (Illinois Drainage Guide, 2022) [55].

Also, although many sources on the internet provide the minimum system requirements, the reality is that we'll need the recommended specifications to ensure the system doesn't crash during the execution of crucial functions on a project.

2. System Requirements for Using GRASS GIS

The system requirements to run GRASS GIS are as follows:

Recommended Computer Settings

1. **Memory (RAM):** 4 GB or more
2. **Disk Space:**
 - 500 MB of free disk space or more depending on the size of your datasets
3. **Processor (CPU):** Modern multi-core processor for better performance
4. **Operating System:**
 - Latest versions of Linux, Windows, or macOS
5. **Graphics:** A capable graphics card for handling large datasets and complex visualizations.

System Components	Minimum	Recommended
Processor (CPU)	Core i3 2.7 GHz	Modern multi-core processor for better performance
Memory (RAM)	8 MB (more is recommended for better performance)	4 GB or more
Hard Disk	100 MB of free disk space <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ ~40 MB for executables ▪ ~40 MB for source code (not required if you install the Linux binaries) ▪ Additional space for data (can vary significantly based on your data needs) 	500 MB of free disk space or more depending on the size of your datasets
Graphic Card	GRASS GIS will run in text mode, but for data displays, you need X (X Window System). Any version of X should work with GRASS GIS	2 GB RAM (NVIDIA GeForce)
Operating System	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Linux kernel versions as old as 1.2.13 (see appendices for specific binaries) ▪ GRASS GIS is also available for Windows and macOS 	Latest versions of Linux, Windows, or macOS

Additional Notes:

- **Dependencies:** Ensure that all required dependencies and libraries for GRASS GIS are installed. This may include GDAL, PROJ, and other geospatial libraries.
- **Display:** For graphical displays, having a proper setup for X Window System (on Linux) or appropriate graphics support on Windows/macOS is essential.

These requirements ensure that we can run GRASS GIS effectively, especially when dealing with large geospatial datasets and performing complex analyses (TLDP, n.d.).

3. System Requirements for Using gvSIG

Here are the system requirements to run gvSIG:

Recommended Computer Settings

1. **Operating System:**
 - Windows, Macintosh, or Linux
2. **Processor (CPU):**
 - Intel Core i5 or higher
3. **Memory (RAM):**
 - 512 MB or more
4. **Disk Space:**
 - 4 GB or more of free disk space, depending on the size of your datasets and projects
5. **Graphics:**
 - Graphics card with 1 GB of RAM or higher (NVIDIA GeForce recommended).

System Components	Minimum	Recommended
Processor (CPU)	Intel Core 2 Duo or equivalent	Intel Core i5 or higher
Memory (RAM)	256 MB	512 MB or more
Hard Disk	2 GB of free disk space	4 GB or more of free disk space, depending on the size of your datasets and projects
Graphic Card	Graphics card with 512 MB of RAM	Graphics card with 1 GB of RAM or higher (NVIDIA GeForce recommended)
Operating System	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▪ Windows 7 or higher▪ Macintosh▪ Linux (various distributions)	Latest versions of Windows, Macintosh, or Linux (Tested in WinXP, Linux Ubuntu 10.04 and Linux Kubuntu 10.04)

Additional Considerations:

- **Java Runtime Environment (JRE):** gvSIG requires Java to run. Ensure you have the latest version of JRE installed on your system.
- **Dependencies:** Ensure all required dependencies and libraries for gvSIG are installed.
- **Screen Resolution:** A minimum screen resolution of 1280x800 is recommended for optimal use of the interface.

These requirements will help ensure that gvSIG runs smoothly, especially when working with large geospatial datasets and performing complex analyses (gvSIG, n.d.).

4. System Requirements for Using MapWindow GIS

MapWindow is an open-source Geographic Information System (GIS) and Application Programming Interface (API) distributed under the Mozilla Public License (MPL). It is built on the Microsoft .NET Framework 2.0 (Ames, Daniel & Michaelis, Christopher & Dunsford, Ted. (2007). Introducing the MapWindow GIS Project. 2. 13-16.).

Here are the system requirements to run MapWindow GIS:

Recommended Computer Settings

1. **Operating System:**
 - Windows 7 or higher (64-bit version for better performance)
2. **Processor (CPU):**
 - Intel Core i5 or higher
3. **Memory (RAM):**
 - 4 GB or more
4. **Disk Space:**
 - 2 GB or more of free disk space, depending on the size of your datasets and projects
5. **Graphics:**
 - Graphics card with 1 GB of RAM or higher (NVIDIA GeForce recommended).

System Components	Minimum	Recommended
Processor (CPU)	Intel Pentium 4 or equivalent	Intel Core i5 or higher
Memory (RAM)	1 GB	4 GB or more
Hard Disk	500 MB of free disk space	2 GB or more of free disk space, depending on the size of your datasets and projects
Graphic Card	Graphics card with 128 MB of RAM	Graphics card with 1 GB of RAM or higher (NVIDIA GeForce recommended)
Operating System	Windows XP or higher (32-bit and 64-bit versions supported)	Windows 7 or higher (64-bit version for better performance)

Additional Considerations:

- **.NET Framework:** MapWindow GIS requires the .NET Framework to run. Ensure you have the latest version of .NET Framework installed on your system.
- **Dependencies:** Make sure all required dependencies and libraries for MapWindow GIS are installed.
- **Screen Resolution:** A minimum screen resolution of 1280x800 is recommended for optimal use of the interface.

These requirements will help ensure that MapWindow GIS runs smoothly.

5. System Requirements for Using uDig

Here are the system requirements to run uDig (User-friendly Desktop Internet GIS):

Recommended Computer Settings

1. **Operating System:**
 - Windows 7 or higher
 - macOS 10.13 (High Sierra) or higher
 - Latest stable version of Linux distributions
2. **Processor (CPU):**
 - Intel Core i5 or higher
3. **Memory (RAM):**
 - 4 GB or more
4. **Disk Space:**

- 1 GB or more of free disk space, depending on the size of your datasets and projects

5. Graphics:

- Graphics card with 512 MB of RAM or higher (NVIDIA GeForce recommended).

System Components	Minimum	Recommended
Processor (CPU)	Intel Pentium 4 or equivalent	Intel Core i5 or higher
Memory (RAM)	2 GB	4 GB or more
Hard Disk	500 MB of free disk space	1 GB or more of free disk space, depending on the size of your datasets and projects
Graphic Card	Graphics card with 128 MB of RAM	Graphics card with 512 MB of RAM or higher (NVIDIA GeForce recommended)
Operating System	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Windows XP or higher ▪ macOS 10.10 (Yosemite) or higher ▪ Linux (various distributions) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Windows 7 or higher ▪ macOS 10.13 (High Sierra) or higher ▪ Latest stable version of Linux distributions

Additional Considerations:

- **Java Runtime Environment (JRE):** uDig requires Java to run. Ensure you have the latest version of JRE installed on your system.
- **Dependencies:** Ensure all required dependencies and libraries for uDig are installed.
- **Screen Resolution:** A minimum screen resolution of 1280x800 is recommended for optimal use of the interface.

These requirements will ensure that uDig operates efficiently, particularly when handling large geospatial datasets.

6. System Requirements for Using OpenJump GIS

Here are the system requirements to run OpenJump GIS (OpenJUMP, n.d.):

Recommended Computer Settings

- 1. Operating System:**
 - Windows 7 or higher
 - Mac OSX
 - Latest stable version of Linux distributions
- 2. Processor (CPU):**
 - Intel Core i5 or higher
- 3. Memory (RAM):**
 - 256 MB or more
- 4. Disk Space:**
 - 500 MB or more of free disk space, depending on the size of your datasets and projects
- 5. Graphics:**
 - Graphics card with 512 MB of RAM or higher (NVIDIA GeForce recommended).

System Components	Minimum	Recommended
Processor (CPU)	Intel Pentium 4 or equivalent	Intel Core i5 or higher
Memory (RAM)	124 MB	256 MB or more
Hard Disk	200 MB of free disk space	500 MB or more of free disk space, depending on the size of your datasets and projects
Graphic Card	Graphics card with 128 MB of RAM	Graphics card with 512 MB of RAM or higher (NVIDIA GeForce recommended)
Operating System	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Windows XP or higher ▪ Mac OSX ▪ Linux (various distributions) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Windows 7 or higher ▪ Mac OSX ▪ Latest stable version of Linux distributions

Additional Considerations:

- **Java Runtime Environment (JRE):** OpenJump GIS requires Java 1.5 to run. Ensure you have the latest version of JRE installed on your system.
- **Additional Java Libraries:** Some plugins could also require the installation of Java(TM) Advanced Imaging (JAI) or Java3D available from <http://java.sun.com/javase/technologies/desktop/media/> (SOLDIN, n.d.)
- **Dependencies:** Ensure all required dependencies and libraries for OpenJump GIS are installed.
- **Screen Resolution:** A minimum screen resolution of 1280x800 is recommended for optimal use of the interface.

Meeting these requirements will ensure OpenJump GIS runs efficiently, especially when dealing with large geospatial datasets and performing complex analyses. (SOLDIN, n.d.)

7. System Requirements for Using FalconView GIS

Here are the system requirements to run FalconView GIS:

Recommended Computer Settings

1. **Operating System:**
 - Windows 10 (64-bit)
2. **Processor (CPU):**
 - Intel Core i5 or higher
3. **Memory (RAM):**
 - 8 GB or more
4. **Disk Space:**
 - 20 GB or more of free disk space, depending on the size of your datasets and projects
5. **Graphics:**
 - Graphics card with 1 GB of RAM or higher (NVIDIA GeForce recommended).

System Components	Minimum	Recommended
Processor (CPU)	Intel Core 2 Duo or equivalent	Intel Core i5 or higher
Memory (RAM)	2 GB	8 GB or more
Hard Disk	10 GB of free disk space	20 GB or more of free disk space, depending on the size of your datasets and projects

Graphic Card	Graphics card with 512 MB of RAM	Graphics card with 1 GB of RAM or higher (NVIDIA GeForce recommended)
Operating System	Windows 7 or higher (64-bit versions recommended)	Windows 10 (64-bit)

Additional Considerations:

- **.NET Framework:** FalconView GIS requires the .NET Framework to run. Ensure you have the latest version of .NET Framework installed on your system.
- **Dependencies:** Ensure all required dependencies and libraries for FalconView GIS are installed.
- **Screen Resolution:** A minimum screen resolution of 1280x800 is recommended for optimal use of the interface.

These requirements will help ensure that FalconView GIS runs smoothly, especially when working with large geospatial datasets and performing complex analyses (Georgia Tech, n.d.).

When comparing the system requirements of all these different GIS software, it is evident that while each has its own minimum and recommended settings, they all require more robust specifications to function properly and avoid crashes during critical operations. A common aspect across all these software packages is the need for additional installations, such as specific libraries (GDAL, PROJ), frameworks (.NET Framework), or runtime environments (Java Environment). Despite these similarities, the software are designed to perform different functions. For example, most of them, except QGIS, do not support extensive vector and attribute editing. Below is a detailed comparison table outlining the common and unique requirements and features of each software.

A comparison table for the system requirements of the above mentioned GIS software:

Component	Minimum Requirements (Common)	Recommended Requirements (Common)	Additional Requirements (Common)	Unique Features/Limitations
Operating System	Windows 7 or higher, macOS 10.10 or higher, Linux	Latest versions of Windows, macOS, or Linux	Specific libraries (GDAL, PROJ), .NET Framework (FalconView), Java Runtime Environment (OpenJump, uDig)	Each software is designed for different functions; QGIS supports extensive vector and attribute editing, others may not
Processor (CPU)	Intel Pentium 4 or equivalent	Intel Core i5 or higher	Proper installation of dependencies	CPU requirements may vary based on the complexity of tasks performed
Memory (RAM)	2 GB	4-8 GB or more	Ensure sufficient memory is available by closing unnecessary applications	Some software may crash or run slow without recommended RAM
Disk Space	200 MB - 10 GB	1-20 GB or more	Additional space may be required based on the size of datasets	Disk space varies based on data and project requirements

Graphics	Graphics card with 128 MB of RAM	Graphics card with 512 MB - 1 GB of RAM or higher	Proper graphics driver installation	Graphics requirements depend on the complexity of visualizations and data sets
Screen Resolution	1280x800	1280x800 or higher	N/A	Higher resolution recommended for optimal interface use
Software Requirements	Installation of specific libraries and dependencies (e.g., GDAL, PROJ, .NET Framework, Java Runtime Environment)	Installation of latest versions of all required libraries and dependencies	Ongoing updates and maintenance of dependencies	Ensure all required software components are up-to-date for smooth operation

Summary:

- ✓ **Common System Requirements:** All software have minimum and recommended settings, typically involving modern operating systems, adequate RAM, and sufficient disk space.
- ✓ **Additional Requirements:** All require specific libraries and dependencies (e.g., GDAL, PROJ, .NET Framework, Java Runtime Environment) to function properly and avoid system crashes.
- ✓ **Unique Features/Limitations:** Each software serves different functions. For example, QGIS allows extensive vector and attribute editing, which is not commonly supported by all other software. On the other hand, some software supports different types of analysis that QGIS may only provide through plugins.

So, it is important to make sure your system meets the recommended requirements to ensure smooth operation and prevent crashes. It is also important to keep all necessary libraries and dependencies up to date for the GIS software to function properly. And lastly, to understand the specific capabilities and limitations of each open-source GIS software, to select the best one for user specific needs.

Let's now explore the commercial ones:

Evaluation of commercial GIS software and the resources required for smooth operation of user procedures;

1. System Requirements for Using ArcMap, part of the Esri ArcGIS Desktop suite

Here are the system requirements to run ArcMap, part of the Esri ArcGIS Desktop suite:

Recommended Computer Settings

1. **Operating System:**
 - Windows 10 (Home, Pro, and Enterprise) (64-bit)
2. **Processor (CPU):**
 - Intel i5, i7, or equivalent AMD processor; hyper-threading (HHT) or multi-core recommended

3. **Memory (RAM):**
 - 8 GB or more
4. **Disk Space:**
 - 6 GB or more of free space
5. **Graphics:**
 - OpenGL 2.0–capable graphics card with 2 GB or higher video memory (NVIDIA GeForce or equivalent).

System Components	Minimum	Recommended
Processor (CPU)	2.2 GHz minimum; hyper-threading (HHT) or multi-core recommended	Intel i5, i7, or equivalent AMD processor; hyper-threading (HHT) or multi-core recommended
Memory (RAM)	4 GB	8 GB or more
Hard Disk	4 GB of free disk space	6 GB or more of free disk space, depending on the size of your datasets and projects
Graphic Card	OpenGL 2.0–capable graphics card with 256 MB or higher video memory	OpenGL 2.0–capable graphics card with 2 GB or higher video memory (NVIDIA GeForce or equivalent)
Operating System	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Windows 10 (Home, Pro, and Enterprise) (64-bit) ▪ Windows 8.1 (Basic, Pro, and Enterprise) (64-bit) ▪ Windows 7 SP1 (Ultimate, Professional, and Enterprise) (64-bit) 	Windows 10 (Home, Pro, and Enterprise) (64-bit)

Additional Considerations:

- **.NET Framework:** ArcMap requires .NET Framework 4.5 or higher.
- **Dependencies:** Ensure all required dependencies and libraries for ArcMap are installed: ArcGIS Desktop requires Microsoft Visual C++ 2015–2019 Redistributable (x86) minimum version 14.22.27821. Obtain the Microsoft Visual C++ Redistributable for Visual Studio 2015–2019 file from the Microsoft site. If the Microsoft Visual C++ 2015–2019 Redistributable (x86) is not already installed, running **setup.exe** will install it before **setup.msi** is launched. **Setup.msi** will not install if Microsoft Visual C++ 2015–2019 Redistributable (x86) is not already installed (Esri, n.d.).
- **Screen Resolution:** A minimum screen resolution of 1024x768 is required, 1920x1080 or higher recommended for optimal use.

These requirements ensure that ArcMap runs smoothly, especially when working with large datasets and performing complex spatial analyses.

2. System Requirements for Using ArcGIS Pro

Here are the system requirements to run ArcGIS Pro:

Recommended Computer Settings

1. **Operating System:**
 - Windows 10 (Home, Pro, and Enterprise) (64-bit)
2. **Processor (CPU):**
 - 4 cores or more (Intel i7 or equivalent AMD processor recommended)

3. **Memory (RAM):**
 - 32 GB or more (64 GB or more recommended for larger projects)
4. **Disk Space:**
 - SSD with 32 GB or more of free space
5. **Graphics:**
 - DirectX 12 with feature level 12_0
 - Shader Model 6.0
 - 8 GB or more dedicated video memory (NVIDIA GeForce GTX 1080 or equivalent).

System Components	Minimum	Recommended
Processor (CPU)	2 cores minimum (Hyper-threading (HHT) or Multi-core recommended)	4 cores or more (Intel i7 or equivalent AMD processor recommended)
Memory (RAM)	8 GB	32 GB or more (64 GB or more recommended for larger projects)
Hard Disk	32 GB of free space	SSD with 32 GB or more of free space
Graphic Card	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ DirectX 11, feature level 11.0 (DirectX 12 is recommended) ▪ Shader Model 5.0 ▪ 4 GB dedicated video memory (DirectX 11 compatible) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ DirectX 12 with feature level 12_0 ▪ Shader Model 6.0 ▪ 8 GB or more dedicated video memory (NVIDIA GeForce GTX 1080 or equivalent)
Operating System	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Windows 10 (Home, Pro, and Enterprise) (64-bit) ▪ Windows 8.1 (Pro and Enterprise) (64-bit) ▪ Windows Server 2019, 2016, 2012 R2 (Standard and Datacenter) 	Windows 10 (Home, Pro, and Enterprise) (64-bit)

Additional Considerations:

- **.NET Framework:** ArcGIS Pro requires .NET Framework 4.8.
- **Dependencies:** Ensure all required dependencies and libraries for ArcGIS Pro are installed.
- **Screen Resolution:** A minimum screen resolution of 1280x800 is required, 1920x1080 or higher recommended for optimal use.

These requirements ensure that ArcGIS Pro runs smoothly, particularly when handling large datasets and performing advanced spatial analyses and 3D visualization (Esri, n.d.).

3. System Requirements for Using MapInfo Pro

Here are the system requirements to run MapInfo Pro:

Recommended Computer Settings

1. **Operating System:**
 - Windows 10 (64-bit)
2. **Processor (CPU):**
 - Intel Core i5 or i7, or equivalent AMD processor
3. **Memory (RAM):**
 - 8 GB or more

4. **Disk Space:**
 - SSD with 4 GB or more of free space
5. **Graphics:**
 - 1 GB or more video memory
 - DirectX 11 compatible

System Components	Minimum	Recommended
Processor (CPU)	Intel Core i3 or equivalent AMD processor	Intel Core i5 or i7, or equivalent AMD processor
Memory (RAM)	4 GB	8 GB or more
Hard Disk	2 GB of free space	SSD with 4 GB or more of free space
Graphic Card	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ 256 MB video memory ▪ DirectX 9.0c compatible 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ 1 GB or more video memory ▪ DirectX 11 compatible
Operating System	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Windows 10 (64-bit) ▪ Windows 8.1 (64-bit) ▪ Windows 7 SP1 (64-bit) ▪ Windows Server 2012, 2016, 2019 	Windows 10 (64-bit)

Additional Considerations:

- **.NET Framework:** MapInfo Pro requires .NET Framework 4.6 or higher.
- **Dependencies:** Ensure all required dependencies and libraries for MapInfo Pro are installed.
- **Screen Resolution:** A minimum screen resolution of 1024x768 is required, 1920x1080 or higher recommended for optimal use.

These requirements ensure that MapInfo Pro runs efficiently, especially when working with large datasets and performing complex spatial analyses.

4. System Requirements for Using Global Mapper

Here are the system requirements to run Global Mapper:

Recommended Computer Settings

1. **Operating System:**
 - Windows 10 (64-bit)
2. **Processor (CPU):**
 - Intel Core i7 or equivalent AMD processor (Quad core)
3. **Memory (RAM):**
 - 8 GB or more (16 GB recommended for large datasets)
4. **Disk Space:**
 - SSD with 2 GB or more of free space
5. **Graphics:**
 - 2 GB or more dedicated video memory
 - OpenGL 4.5 compatible graphics card

System Components	Minimum	Recommended
Processor (CPU)	1.0 GHz processor (Single core)	Intel Core i7 or equivalent AMD processor (Quad core)

Memory (RAM)	4 GB	8 GB or more (16 GB recommended for large datasets)
Hard Disk	400 MB for installation	SSD with 2 GB or more of free space
Graphic Card	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ 256 MB video memory ▪ OpenGL 3.3 compatible graphics card 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ 2 GB or more dedicated video memory ▪ OpenGL 4.5 compatible graphics card
Operating System	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Windows 7 SP1 ▪ Windows 8 ▪ Windows 10 ▪ Windows Server 2008/2012/2016/2019 	Windows 10 (64-bit)

Additional Considerations:

- **Screen Resolution:** A minimum screen resolution of 1024x768 is required, 1920x1080 or higher recommended for optimal use.
- **Dependencies:** Ensure all required dependencies and libraries for Global Mapper are installed.
- **Optional:** An internet connection is required for accessing online data sources and for software updates.

So, below is a comparative table of the important features and system requirements common to all four commercial GIS software: ArcMap, ArcGIS Pro, MapInfo Pro, and Global Mapper.

Feature	ArcMap	ArcGIS Pro	MapInfo Pro	Global Mapper
Operating System	Windows 7-10, Server 2012-2019	Windows 7-10, Server 2012-2019	Windows 7-10, Server 2012-2019	Windows 7-10, Server 2008-2019
Processor (CPU)	2.2 GHz (i3/i5/i7 recommended)	2 cores (i5/i7 recommended)	i3 (i5/i7 recommended)	1.0 GHz (i7 recommended)
Memory (RAM)	4 GB (8 GB recommended)	4 GB (8 GB recommended)	4 GB (8 GB recommended)	4 GB (8 GB recommended)
Disk Space	4 GB (6 GB recommended)	32 GB (SSD recommended)	2 GB (4 GB recommended, SSD)	400 MB (2 GB recommended, SSD)
Graphics	256 MB (1 GB recommended)	4 GB (8 GB recommended)	256 MB (1 GB recommended)	256 MB (2 GB recommended)
Graphics Compatibility	DirectX 9.0c	DirectX 11 (DirectX 12 recommended)	DirectX 9.0c	OpenGL 3.3 (OpenGL 4.5 recommended)
Screen Resolution	1024x768 (1920x1080 recommended)	1280x800 (1920x1080 recommended)	1024x768 (1920x1080 recommended)	1024x768 (1920x1080 recommended)
.NET Framework	4.5 or higher	4.8	4.6 or higher	Not specified
Dependencies	Required libraries and	Required libraries and	Required libraries and	Required libraries and

	dependencies	dependencies	dependencies	dependencies
Additional Requirements	External libraries like GDAL, PROJ	External libraries like GDAL, PROJ	External libraries like GDAL, PROJ	External libraries like GDAL, PROJ

Common Considerations

- **Ensure recommended system requirements:** Meeting the recommended system requirements is crucial for smooth operation and to prevent crashes during critical tasks.
- **Keep necessary libraries and dependencies updated:** All GIS software rely on external libraries (e.g., GDAL, PROJ) and frameworks (e.g., .NET) for full functionality.

Listed below is a comparative table that highlights the commonalities and unique aspects of open-source and commercial GIS software, providing a clear understanding of what each category offers and what sets them apart.

Comparative Table of Common and Unique Features of Open-Source and Commercial GIS Software

Feature	Common (Open-Source & Commercial)	Unique (Open-Source)	Unique (Commercial)
Minimum System Requirements	All GIS software have minimum system requirements that must be met for basic functionality.	Typically more flexible in terms of system requirements.	Often have higher minimum system requirements due to more advanced features.
Recommended System Requirements	All GIS software have recommended system requirements for optimal performance.	Often can function reasonably well on lower-end hardware.	Generally require higher-end hardware for optimal performance.
Dependencies	All GIS software may require additional libraries and dependencies such as GDAL, PROJ, Java, .NET Framework, etc.	Often have more dependencies due to the community-driven nature of development.	Dependencies are usually bundled or managed more seamlessly.
Vector and Attribute Editing	Basic vector and attribute editing capabilities are available.	Typically, more limited in extensive vector and attribute editing	Extensive vector and attribute editing capabilities, often more user-friendly.

		Open Source	Proprietary
		functionalities.	
Data Management	Basic data management tools are available.	Usually have a wide range of plugins and extensions to enhance data management.	Integrated, comprehensive data management tools, often with proprietary enhancements.
Support and Documentation	Both have support and documentation, though quality and availability can vary.	Community support is often robust, but documentation may vary in quality.	Professional support and extensive, high-quality documentation are typically available.
Cost	Both can be costly in terms of hardware and resource requirements.	Free to use, but may have costs associated with advanced features or support.	Requires a purchase or subscription, often with higher upfront and ongoing costs.
Flexibility	Both offer a degree of flexibility in terms of customization and use cases.	Highly flexible and customizable, often through plugins and community contributions.	Customizable through official extensions and support, but within the bounds of the software ecosystem.
User Interface	Both offer user interfaces that range from basic to advanced.	Interfaces may vary greatly and can be less intuitive for beginners.	Typically more polished and user-friendly interfaces designed for a smoother user experience.
Updates and Maintenance	Regular updates and maintenance are common.	Updates driven by community contributions, can be frequent but may lack consistency.	Regular, consistent updates and maintenance, usually with guaranteed support.
Performance	Performance can be highly variable based on system specs and software optimization.	Can be optimized for lower-end systems but may require tweaking.	Generally optimized for performance on higher-end systems.
Integration with Other Tools	Integration with other tools and software is possible but varies.	Often integrates well with other open-source tools and platforms.	Designed to integrate seamlessly with other commercial software and enterprise systems.

An important question arises here: What does it mean to rely on external libraries? Should developers make code dependent on external libraries?

Relying on Third-Party Code Libraries

When deciding whether to add a dependency to a project, it's essential to have a strategy. Too often, developers reach for an existing library to minimize work when a client requests a new feature. While this can be efficient, it can also lead to future maintenance headaches.

Taking Responsibility for Third-Party Code

When you add a third-party library, you're taking on responsibility for code you didn't write. This can introduce potential liabilities and complexities. Every new piece of code increases overhead, whether in load time or complexity.

Third-party libraries often contain more code than necessary because they're designed to handle a wide range of use cases. This extra, unused code can make your project more cumbersome and introduce more opportunities for bugs. Plus, each library may have its own dependencies, creating a complex web of code to manage and maintain.

All in all, we'll arrange the main challenges as main disadvantages in the following order:

1. Dependency Issues

Relying on a third-party library ties your code to that specific library. If you ever need to switch to a different library, you might have to make significant changes to your code. One way to manage this is by using a facade (wrapper), so your code interacts with an abstraction instead of the library directly.

2. Support Problems

A library might be abandoned by its author, which can be a big problem, especially for platforms like Android that have frequent updates. Libraries need regular maintenance to stay compatible with the latest SDK versions. Without this, they may not work well, or at all, on newer devices.

3. Overuse

Using too many libraries can lead to dependency conflicts that are hard to fix. An excess of libraries can also bloat your app, increasing its size and memory consumption, which can hurt performance. For Android apps, this can even contribute to hitting the 64k methods limit.

4. Security Risks

Third-party libraries can also introduce security risks. Open-source libraries can be targets for hackers, so it's important to ensure they are secure and regularly updated.

Impact on Algorithm Efficiency and Green Software Development

Using third-party libraries can impact the efficiency of your algorithms and the overall goal of achieving green software development. Here's how:

Efficiency Concerns

- **Resource Overhead:** Third-party libraries often include more functionality than you need, which can lead to increased resource consumption. This added overhead can slow down your software, making it less efficient.

- **Dependency Management:** Managing multiple dependencies can complicate your codebase and introduce inefficiencies. Conflicts between libraries can lead to performance issues, requiring more resources to resolve.

Green Software Development

- **Energy Consumption:** Inefficient algorithms and bloated code from unnecessary library functions can increase energy consumption. Optimizing your code by minimizing dependencies helps reduce the environmental footprint.
- **Sustainability:** Using well-maintained and efficient libraries aligns with the principles of green software development. Ensure the libraries you choose are actively supported and optimized for performance.

Software-Specific Capabilities

However, each GIS software is tailored to execute different functions. Therefore, we need to extend our research by running similar, if not identical, tools with the same dataset in a few of these software platforms.

To begin our exploration, we'll start with QGIS, one of the most commonly and widely used open-source GIS platforms. Next, we'll compare its capabilities with SGIS technology.

Task #1 – GIS Data creation

One essential GIS task is data creation, which involves inputting points, lines, and polygons. This can be done manually or automatically. Digitizing is a task we cannot imagine GIS without, so let's start with creating polygons.

In GIS, polygons are a vital element, serving various purposes from delineating countries and regions to representing urban parcels and more.

Fig.3 A DXF file loaded in QGIS, consisting of line features that need to be converted into polygon features. We start by cleaning the geometry and removing any duplicates.

A polygon is essentially a closed polyline, where the starting and ending coordinates coincide. For effective use, polygons should exhibit simplicity, meaning they should not have self-intersections, and the file should be cleaned of any duplicate geometry.

Fig.4 The function for cleaning up duplicates is in progress, but the algorithm is taking more than 5 minutes to complete.

This quality ensures their accuracy and usefulness in Geographic Information Systems.

In our example, we are focusing on the cadastral municipality of Demir Kapija, which includes both a rural area (arable land) and an urban, populated section. For this illustration, we exported vector CAD files in DXF format. These files contain various elements such as lines representing cadastral parcels, cadastral objects, contour lines, municipal boundaries, parcel numbers, and object numbers. To keep things organized, these elements are grouped into separate CAD layers.

When we import these files into QGIS, the software separates the layers into different entity types. However, QGIS does not maintain the original groupings from the CAD file. Instead, it groups all lines into line entities, all labels and points into point entities, and polygons, if any, into polygon entities.

Fig.5 After cleaning the duplicate geometries, we've created a clean temporary layer. From this layer, we will proceed with executing the Lines to Polygons algorithm.

This is why, when you try to create polygons for the entire municipality, the line entities layer contains multiple CAD line layers. This complexity makes the Lines to Polygons algorithm inefficient.

People often encounter challenges when importing DXF CAD files into QGIS because all line entities, point entities, and polygon entities are grouped into one common layer. This grouping can make it difficult to obtain the desired map, as it loses the original CAD layer distinctions.

To address this, users typically clean the DXF file first before exporting and importing it into GIS software. They often export only one CAD layer at a time to maintain clarity.

For instance, in our example, one might export only the parcels layer to avoid ending up with multiple line layers merged into one. By doing so, they ensure a more manageable and accurate import into the GIS system.

Fig.6 When executing the Lines to Polygons function, an error occurs. Although a polygon layer is created in the layer panel, it is empty and no polygons appear in the graphics panel.

To simplify the process and follow common practice, we'll export only the parcel layer from the DXF file. This way, when we import it into QGIS, we'll have just one line layer to work with.

Fig.7 We added another layer, this time containing only parcels. We'll attempt to run the Lines to Polygons function again.

Despite having only the desired layer imported and selected, the algorithm still fails to execute the command and generate polygons from the input lines. An error message stating "one or more lines ignored due to geometry not having a minimum of three vertices" appears.

Fig.8 An error message appears when attempting to execute the Lines to Polygons command.

In cases like this, users commonly employ a method to rectify geometry issues using a 'Fix Geometry' function and then utilize an alternative algorithm to polygonize the vector data.

The 'Fix Geometries' algorithm aims to "Attempt to create a valid representation of a given invalid geometry without losing any of the input vertices. Already-valid geometries are returned without further intervention. Always outputs multi-geometry layer. M values will be dropped from the output."

However, SGIS simplifies this process by directly creating polygons without requiring users to take extra steps or use additional fixing functions.

Let's explore further to understand what the Fixing Algorithm actually does. Essentially, it corrects geometry by using the makeValid method, ensuring geometry correction without losing nodes.

According to the OGC Simple Feature Access specification, geometries must adhere to OpenGIS compliance standards (refer to PostGIS docs for quick reference). Here are the key predicates:

- Points are inherently valid.
- LineStrings are valid if they are simple, meaning they do not pass through an inner vertex more than once.
- Polygons are valid if their linear components are simple and their rings do not cross.
- MultiPoints are valid if each coordinate pair is unique.
- MultiLineStrings are simple if all components are simple and share common vertices.
- MultiPolygons are valid if all components are valid and do not overlap.

To achieve this, the internally used GEOS modules perform the following operations:

- Correctly node a LineString by removing consecutive duplicated vertices.

- Node the linear components of a Polygon and reconstruct valid areas iteratively.
- Apply these operations to all parts of Multi geometries.

Noding involves breaking a linear component at non-consecutive duplicated vertices. In this context, "fixing" geometries means creating the largest possible set of their valid and/or simple parts, which may result in a collection of geometries of different dimensionalities.

Now, let's explore how SGIS Technology manages this functionality;

We begin by importing the DXF file into the software.

Fig.9 After importing the DXF file into SGIS Desktop, we observe three distinct layers: Points, Polylines, and Polygons

Next, we utilize the 'Separate DXF layers into GIS layers' function, a convenient one-click operation. Selecting any of the three layers—Points, Polylines, or Polygons—and activating this function automatically unpacks all original CAD layers, importing them into GIS with their original colors and layer names intact.

In our example, we'll unpack the polyline layer, which contains multiple polyline layers within it. All these layers will be visible in the Layers Panel, retaining their original names from the CAD drawing.

Our goal is to locate 'Polyline Level 11,' specifically representing the Cadastral Parcels.

We'll proceed to convert these polyline features into polygons, similar to our approach in QGIS.

Fig.10 All original polyline layers have been unpacked from the Polyline Layer.

After the layers are displayed in the Layers Panel, the next step is to select the desired layer by clicking on with the blue-colored selection within the Panel. Once selected, activate the Lines to Polygons function.

This action opens a new dialog box where we need to ensure the "Remove duplicates" option is checked, as we haven't yet cleaned up or removed duplicate geometries from the layer. Then, click on "Convert" to initiate the process.

Fig.11 Converting Lines to Polygons

Fig.12 Polygons have been successfully created, appearing as a new layer in the Layers Panel.

Why does the first software require geometry fixing while the second generates polygons without additional steps?

Algorithms designed for a wide user base often encounter such issues. They aim to handle diverse inputs and scenarios, which can lead to errors or the need for adjustments. This is particularly common in software solutions dealing with various data types and scenarios, where specific configurations may require extra handling or fixing to ensure accurate results. Users may need to apply additional fixes or preprocessing steps to align with the algorithm's requirements and ensure optimal performance and correctness in their workflows.

However, efficient algorithms minimize the need for additional fixes and preprocessing steps, thereby reducing the use of computational resources. This reduction helps lower the environmental footprint of computing processes and aligns with Green IT goals of optimizing resource use and energy efficiency. By ensuring algorithms operate effectively with minimal extra steps, we can support more sustainable computing practices.

A more focused and efficient approach for specific tasks, reduces the need for additional steps and computational resources. This aligns better with Green IT principles. In contrast, open-source and designed for a broader user base algorithms and functions, offer versatility but often require extra processing and handling, which can impact efficiency and sustainability.

Here's a comparison table highlighting (for this specific use case) the differences between a focused and effective algorithm, and the more generalized algorithm:

Feature (Lines to Polygons)	SGIS (Focused and Effective Algorithm)	QGIS (Generalized and Open-Source Algorithm)
Data Handling	Directly handles CAD layers, retains original colors and layer names.	Converts all lines, points, and polygons into separate entities, losing original layer groupings.
Ease of Use	One-click function to separate DXF layers into GIS layers.	Requires manual cleaning and preparation of data before processing.
Geometry Validation	Automatically creates valid polygons without additional fixes.	Often encounters errors requiring geometry fixing and preprocessing steps.
Efficiency	High efficiency, optimized for specific tasks without needing extra steps.	Less efficient, often requires additional interventions to ensure accuracy.
Algorithm Robustness	Focused on specific use cases, leading to more reliable and accurate results.	Designed to handle a wide range of scenarios, which can lead to potential errors and inefficiencies.
Environmental Impact	Minimizes computational resources, supporting Green IT goals.	Increased computational resource use due to additional preprocessing steps.
User Base	Tailored for a niche user base, often professional users.	Aimed at a broad user base, including hobbyists and professionals.
Support and Updates	Regular updates focused on enhancing specific functionalities.	Community-driven updates, may vary in frequency and focus.
Cost	Typically commercial software with associated costs.	Open-source and free to use, but may require investment in training and support, and additional plug-ins.

Task #2 – Lidar & Remote Sensing data management

Lidar (light detection and ranging) is an optical remote-sensing method that uses laser light to measure distances to the Earth's surface. It's commonly used in airborne laser mapping as an alternative to traditional surveying techniques. A lidar system includes a laser scanner, GPS, and inertial navigation system (INS). Lidar data, processed into highly accurate 3D points, includes various attributes like intensity, return number, and classification. The technology captures multiple returns from objects, helping to create detailed terrain and surface models.

LiDAR point-cloud data provide detailed, high-resolution information about the Earth's surface, including terrain, buildings, and vegetation. These data are incredibly versatile and can be used to enhance GIS analysis in a wide range of fields.

To conduct our research, we'll compare algorithm effectiveness and system requirements using a LiDAR dataset. We'll start by examining the open-source option, then compare it with the commercial alternative.

Understanding the LAS File Format

The LAS file format is a widely recognized public file format designed for the interchange of 3-dimensional point cloud data. Initially developed for the exchange of LiDAR point cloud data, LAS supports the transfer of any 3-dimensional x, y, z coordinates. As a binary file format, LAS provides an efficient alternative to proprietary systems and generic ASCII file formats commonly used by various companies.

ASCII file interchange, although widely used, has two major drawbacks: slow performance due to the extensive processing time required for reading and interpreting ASCII elevation

data, and the excessively large file sizes that result from even small data sets. Furthermore, ASCII formats fail to retain the specific information integral to LiDAR data.

In contrast, the LAS file format preserves the essential details specific to LiDAR data without introducing undue complexity. The LAS 1.4 Specification [48], approved by the ASPRS Board on November 14, 2011, remains the latest sanctioned version.

For our second research task, we'll be using a file in the LAS format. Here are the file information:

LAS version: 1.4

of points: 9 212 883

Point type: 6

Point size: 30

Compression: none

of 1st returns: 7 610 968

of 2nd returns: 1 274 594

of 3rd returns: 279 415

of 4th returns: 43 629

of 5th returns: 4 065

Let's begin by importing the LAS data into QGIS. The process is very straightforward, thanks to the drag and drop function. Once the LAS file is loaded, the point cloud is displayed with its classifications.

However, QGIS initially opens all possible classifications from the list, even if the file doesn't contain all those classes. To ensure the correct classifications are displayed, we need to delete all existing classifications and then reclassify the data. This time, only the existing classifications will be shown, and we can choose different colors for each class individually.

Fig.13 Opening a LAS file in QGIS, all classifications are displayed in the Layers panel.

This is how the classifications appear after deleting the auto-generated list, showing only the valid ones:

Fig.14 The Layers Panel displaying the existing classifications after removing the auto-generated list. @Principles of Energy-Efficient Algorithms and Data Structures

The next step is to proceed to the 'Ground Filter' algorithm. Filtering ground points is a fundamental task. QGIS itself lacks an algorithm for this but can utilize the open-source tool LASTools by rapidlasso, available as a plug-in that users must manually install and connect to QGIS. However, not all of LASTools' features are open-source. Some tools are free, while others require a license to function. Here is the list of tools as provided on their official webpage:

Tool overview

Open source tools

- laszip** compresses LAS files to LAZ in high speed without information loss
- las2las** filters, transforms, subsamples, clips, thins, ...
- las2txt** turns LAS/LAZ into human-readable and easy-to-parse text
- txt2las** converts LiDAR from standard ASCII to LAS/LAZ
- lascopcindex** creates a COPC *.laz file for a given set of *.las or *.laz files
- lasdiff** compares LIDAR data of two LAS/LAZ/ASCII files and reports whether they are identical or whether they are different
- lasinfo** prints out an overview of the contents of a LAS/LAZ file
- lasmerge** can merge several LAS/LAZ files into one
- lasprecision** reads LIDAR data in the LAS format and computes statistics about precision "advertised" in the header

Free tools

- lasview** visualizes the contents of a LAS/LAZ file and can also compute a TIN
- lasvalidate** determine if LAS files are conform to the ASPRS LAS specifications
- demzip** compresses and uncompresses raster data to RasterLAZ format

e572las extracts the points from the E57 format and stores them as LAS/LAZ files

Closed source tools

<u>las2dem</u>	rasters pointclouds (via a TIN) into elevation/slope/intensity/RGB DEMs
<u>las2iso</u>	extracts, optionally simplified, elevation contours
<u>las2shp</u>	turns LAS/LAZ into ESRI's Shapefile format
<u>shp2las</u>	turns an ESRI's Shapefile into LAS/LAZ
<u>las2tin</u>	triangulates the points of a LAS/LAZ file into a TIN
<u>lasboundary</u>	computes a boundary polygon
<u>lascanopy</u>	computes popular forestry metrics and grids them onto a raster
<u>lasclassify</u>	classifies buildings and high vegetation (i.e. trees)
<u>lasclip</u>	clips away points falling into polygonal shapes (e.g. building footprints)
<u>lascolor</u>	colors LiDAR points based on imagery
<u>lascontrol</u>	computes the height at certain x and y control points and reports the difference
<u>lascopy</u>	copies attributes using the GPS-time stamp and the return number
<u>lasdatum</u>	transforms from one horizontal datum to another
<u>lasdistance</u>	classifies, flags, or removes points based on distance from polygonal segments
<u>lasduplicate</u>	removes all duplicate points from a LAS/LAZ/ASCII file
<u>lasgrid</u>	grids data onto a raster
<u>lasground</u>	tool for bare-earth extraction
<u>lasground</u>	redesigned version of lasground for even better bare-earth extraction
<u>lasheight</u>	computes the height of each LAS point above the ground
<u>lasindex</u>	creates a *.lax file for a given *.las or *.laz file that contains spatial indexing information
<u>laslayers</u>	add layer functionality to LAS/LAZ files
<u>lasnoise</u>	flags or removes noise points in LAS/LAZ/BIN/ASCII files
<u>lasoptimize</u>	optimizes data for better compression and spatial coherency
<u>lasoverage</u>	finds the "overage" of a airborne collect that get covered by multiple flightline
<u>lasoverlap</u>	checks flight line overlap and/or vertical and horizontal alignment
<u>lasplanes</u>	finds planar patches of LAS/LAZ points fulfilling a number of user-defineable criteria
<u>lasprobe</u>	probes the elevation of the LIDAR for a given x and y location and reports it to a text file or to stdout
<u>laspublish</u>	do 3D visualization of LiDAR data in a web browser using the WebGL Potree
<u>lasreturn</u>	reports geometric return statistics and repairs 'number of returns' field based on GPS times
<u>lassort</u>	z-orders LAS/LAZ files
<u>lassplit</u>	splits the input file(s) into several output files based on various parameters
<u>lasthin</u>	implements a simple point thinning algorithm
<u>lastile</u>	creates a tiling of LAS/LAZ files
<u>lastrack</u>	takes files together with a trajectory file by matching GPS time stamps
<u>lasvdatum</u>	transforms LiDAR from ellipsoidal to orthometric elevations using a grid
<u>lasvoxel</u>	computes a voxelization of points

and even
more...

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Fig.15 A table showcasing the tools available from rapidlasso. The LASTools plug-in is utilized to manage LIDAR data within QGIS. Data Source: [LASTools\[https://lastools.github.io/\]](https://lastools.github.io/)

As we mentioned previously, filtering is a crucial post-processing step for various applications of Light Detection and Ranging (LiDAR) data. For our research, we need to investigate this procedure, in GIS environments. Specifically, we will evaluate how effectively the algorithm performs the filtering function and the amount of resources it consumes. This will involve comparing the execution efficiency and resource requirements in different GIS platforms.

Ground Filtering Algorithms*

Ground filtering algorithms help separate ground from non-ground data in LiDAR datasets. Key considerations for selecting a ground filter include the number and type of LiDAR returns, preprocessing steps, input data format, iterative characteristics, and neighborhood definitions. These factors ensure accurate ground filtering in LiDAR data analysis.

Choosing the right LiDAR return for ground filtering is crucial. Although multiple returns are often available, most researchers prefer the first return for ground filtering. However, in forestry applications, the second, last, or a combination of first and last returns are sometimes used because they penetrate the tree canopy more effectively, providing a better representation of the ground surface. The technique for searching a local LiDAR neighborhood is crucial to capturing the height context of ground features. This context is defined by local neighborhood functions such as linear, circular, or rectangular windows. Studies have shown that the neighborhood size significantly impacts ground filtering performance. Techniques include varying window sizes and assigning weights to points within a neighborhood to determine height context, and progressive morphology with increasing window sizes. Most algorithms iteratively adjust neighborhood size to enhance filtering accuracy.

I'll utilize the categorization of LiDAR ground filtering algorithms by [Meng, Currit, and Zhao](#), which covers various applications and surface types, as well as outlines common processes and critical considerations faced during practical implementations:

- **Directional Scanning Filters [39-40]**

Directional scanning filters typically define neighborhoods in a two-dimensional space, but some methods calculate slope and elevation differences along a one-dimensional scan line. Shan and Sampath [Shan, J.; Sampath, A. Urban DEM generation from raw LiDAR data: a labeling algorithm and its performance. *Photogramm. Eng. Remote Sens.* **2005**, *71*, 217–226. [\[Google Scholar\]](#) [\[CrossRef\]](#)]; developed a bidirectional algorithm that removes non-ground points by calculating slope and elevation differences along the scan line, referencing the nearest ground-labeled point and the label of the previous point. This method compares points with their immediate neighbors, effectively removing low vegetation. However, directional methods can be sensitive to sudden ground surface changes, sometimes creating artificial lines across surfaces. To address the limitations of directional methods, Meng et al. [Meng, X. A slope- and elevation-based filter to remove non-ground measurements from airborne LIDAR data. In *Proceedings of ISPRS WG III/3, III/4, V/3 Workshop "Laser scanning 2005"*, The Netherlands, September 2005; p. 23.] developed a multi-directional ground filtering (MGF) algorithm that combines directional scanning with two-dimensional neighborhood searches by transforming point clouds into raster data. This

hybrid approach preserves object shape, reduces errors within objects, and is robust to threshold selection, effectively removing low vegetation. Unlike traditional two-dimensional methods requiring changing window sizes, the MGF algorithm works well with a fixed three-by-three window, regardless of building sizes.

- **Contour-Based Filters [39-40]**

Contour-based filtering, incorporating methods like active shape models, has been recently applied to LiDAR-based terrain mapping. This technique uses active contours [Elmqvist, M.; Jungert, E.; Lantz, F.; Persson, A.; Soderman, U. Terrain modelling and analysis using laser scanner data. *Int. Arch. Photogramm. Remote Sens.* **2001**, XXXIV, 211–218. [\[Google Scholar\]](#)] to create a three-dimensional contour net that gradually removes non-ground points based on gravitational and attraction forces. These filters offer a novel approach to mapping ground surfaces with LiDAR data. However, further research is needed to evaluate their performance across various surface conditions and to compare their effectiveness with existing algorithms.

- **TIN-Based Filters [39-40]**

The despise Virtual Deforestation (VDF) algorithm is an iterative TIN-based filter designed to remove non-ground points by assessing ground smoothness [Haugerud, R.A.; Harding, D.J. Some algorithms for virtual deforestation (VDF) of LiDAR topographic survey data. *Int. Arch. Photogramm. Remote Sens.* **2001**, XXXIV, 219–226. [\[Google Scholar\]](#)]. It assumes ground surfaces are typically smooth and free of sharp corners. The algorithm builds a TIN model, converts it into a point database and a grid, and calculates mean values within a 3x3 window. Points with strong curvature are flagged as non-ground, with two thresholds for eliminating above-ground points and "negative blunders." The process repeats until no more points are removed, refining the TIN model iteratively.

This filter can process the first, last, or multiple LiDAR returns. It effectively removes small buildings and most bridges but struggles with large, low buildings due to a fixed window size. The filter calculates mean values using a 3x3 window, which fails to capture larger objects. Additionally, it has difficulty removing "negative blunders," extremely low values compared to local points, often dismissed as noise in preprocessing.

A groundbreaking approach developed by Axelsson [Axelsson, P. Processing of laser scanner data-algorithms and applications. *ISPRS J. Photogramm. Remote Sens.* **1999**, 54, 138–147. [\[Google Scholar\]](#) [\[CrossRef\]](#)], Axelsson, P. DEM Generation from Laser Scanner Data Using Adaptive TIN Models. *Int. Arch. Photogramm. Remote Sens.* **2000**, XXXIII, 110–117. [\[Google Scholar\]](#)], known as the active-TIN model, has recently gained prominence in a comparative study of eight ground filtering algorithms. This method utilizes a Triangulated Irregular Network (TIN) to iteratively estimate ground surfaces. It works by gradually identifying and removing non-ground points based on their elevation differences and angles relative to nearby triangles.

What sets this method apart is its adaptive thresholding mechanism, which adjusts dynamically based on the latest ground points discovered in each iteration. This approach offers flexibility and precision, moving beyond traditional fixed thresholds. Experimental results from studies conducted at fifteen different sites confirm that the active-TIN model consistently delivers the highest average overall accuracy [41]. Similar performance superiority was observed when comparing it to two other widely-used methods [42, 43].

Iterative TIN-Based Automatic Filtering of Sparse LiDAR Data [Iterative TIN-Based Automatic Filtering of Sparse LiDAR Data [Belkhouche, Yassine & Buckles, Bill. (2011). Iterative TIN-based automatic filtering of sparse LiDAR data. *Remote Sensing Letters.* 2. 231-240. 10.1080/01431161.2010.515266.]] ; This

method automates the separation of terrain points and object points in sparse Light Detection and Ranging (LiDAR) data by first triangulating raw LiDAR points into a Triangulated Irregular Network (TIN). Each triangle is classified as either an edge triangle or non-edge triangle based on its slope, serving as a discriminative function. Edge triangles occur at the boundary between terrain and non-terrain points, featuring vertices that include both terrain and object points.

Initially, lower points are categorized as terrain, while higher points are classified as objects. An interpolation method adjusts the elevation of object points using estimated local slopes derived from adjacent non-edge triangles. The slopes of modified triangles are recalculated to integrate the adjusted elevations. This iterative process continues until no triangles are classified as edge triangles.

Validation involves assessing type I errors (terrain points misclassified as object points) and type II errors (object points misclassified as terrain points). The method has been tested on multiple extensive datasets containing diverse and intricate objects, consistently achieving an overall accuracy exceeding 90% with an average error rate below 10%.

A revised progressive TIN densification for filtering airborne LiDAR data [Nie, Sheng & Wang, Cheng & Dong, Pinliang & Xi, Xiaohuan & Luo, Shezhou & Qin, Haiming. (2017). A revised progressive TIN densification for filtering airborne LiDAR data. *Measurement*. 104. 10.1016/j.measurement.2017.03.007.] ; Progressive triangular irregular network (TIN) densification (PTD) is a commonly used algorithm for filtering airborne discrete-return LiDAR data. Lasground uses an algorithm based on Axelsson's 2000 Triangulated Irregular Network (TIN) refinement method to effectively identify ground points from dense point cloud datasets. The algorithm starts by selecting initial seed points that seem to represent the ground surface. These points kick off the process of building a TIN model, which is like creating a mesh that connects nearby points to form a surface. As the algorithm progresses, it adds neighboring points that fit within a specified search area and meet a certain angle criterion. This iterative process refines the TIN model to better match the actual ground surface, making it smoother and more accurate.

The algorithm relies on geometric principles of triangulation to interpolate a continuous surface from individual data points. By adjusting the TIN structure and including new points that fit the criteria for ground points, what is achieved is a precise classification. This method efficiently manages large datasets while maintaining high accuracy in terrain modeling.

Here are some known algorithms for LiDAR data processing:

1. Iterative TIN-Based Automatic Filtering of Sparse LiDAR Data

[Belkhouche, Yassine & Buckles, Bill. (2011). Iterative TIN-based automatic filtering of sparse LiDAR data. *Remote Sensing Letters*. 2. 231-240. 10.1080/01431161.2010.515266.]

2. A revised progressive TIN densification for filtering airborne LiDAR data

[Nie, Sheng & Wang, Cheng & Dong, Pinliang & Xi, Xiaohuan & Luo, Shezhou & Qin, Haiming. (2017). A revised progressive TIN densification for filtering airborne LiDAR data. *Measurement*. 104. 10.1016/j.measurement.2017.03.007.]

3. Segmentation of airborne laser scanning data using a slope adaptive neighborhood.

[Filin, S.; Pfeifer, N. Segmentation of airborne laser scanning data using a slope adaptive neighborhood. ISPRS J. Photogramm. Remote Sens. 2009, 60, 71–80. [Google Scholar] [CrossRef]]

4. Some algorithms for virtual deforestation (VDF) of LiDAR topographic survey data.

[Haugerud, R.A.; Harding, D.J. Some algorithms for virtual deforestation (VDF) of LiDAR topographic survey data. Int. Arch. Photogramm. Remote Sens. 2001, XXXIV, 219–226. [Google Scholar]]

5. Processing of laser scanner data-algorithms and applications

[Axelsson, P. Processing of laser scanner data-algorithms and applications. ISPRS J. Photogramm. Remote Sens. 1999, 54, 138–147. [Google Scholar] [CrossRef]]

6. DEM Generation from Laser Scanner Data Using Adaptive TIN Models.

[Axelsson, P. DEM Generation from Laser Scanner Data Using Adaptive TIN Models. Int. Arch. Photogramm. Remote Sens. 2000, XXXIII, 110–117. [Google Scholar]]

7. Experimental comparison of filter algorithms for bare earth extraction from airborne laser scanning point clouds.

[Sithole, G.; Vosselman, G. Experimental comparison of filter algorithms for bare earth extraction from airborne laser scanning point clouds. ISPRS J. Photogramm. Remote Sens. 2004, 59, 85–101. [Google Scholar] [CrossRef]]

Ground Filtering Algorithms and GIS

Despite their importance, ground filtering algorithms are not implemented directly in QGIS, the most commonly used open-source GIS software. While these algorithms are effective, a regular QGIS user cannot complete this task without additional installations. This requires extra computational resources, installation skills, and licenses for certain tools. Thus, a fundamental task like ground filtering becomes less accessible and more resource-intensive for QGIS users.

Starting from version 20.0, QGIS supports the data formats Entwine Point Tile (EPT) and LAS/LAZ for working with point clouds. In QGIS, point cloud data is always saved in the EPT format, which consists of several files stored in a common folder. EPT uses indexing to allow quick access to the data. For more information on the EPT format, see the Entwine homepage (Development of an outline detection tool, 2015).

If the data is in LAS or LAZ format, QGIS converts it to EPT upon the first load. Depending on the file size, this conversion may take some time. During this process, a subfolder is created in the folder containing the LAS/LAZ file, named according to the scheme ept_ + name_LAS/LAZ_file. If such a subfolder already exists, QGIS loads the EPT immediately, resulting in reduced loading time.

What is stated on the official User Manual Documentation page, as worth knowing is that: in QGIS 20.0 and newer versions, it is not yet possible to edit point clouds directly. For point cloud manipulation, users can use CloudCompare, an open-source point cloud processing tool, or the Point Data Abstraction Library (PDAL), which offers command-line options for editing point clouds.

Due to the large number of data points, it is not feasible to display an attribute table of point clouds in QGIS.

For more details on point cloud properties in QGIS 20.0 and above, users can refer to the official documentation (Development of an outline detection tool, 2015).

Considering this, one might wonder why GIS software often doesn't integrate LiDAR tools? One of the primary challenges lies in handling the massive datasets generated by LiDAR and Remote Sensing technology. These datasets consist of millions of data points, resulting in large volumes of data that can be cumbersome to manage and process.

For any GIS platform to effectively integrate LiDAR tools, it must possess the capability to handle such vast datasets without compromising performance. This entails efficient data storage, robust data management capabilities, and sufficient computing resources available to users. Additionally, the development of efficient algorithms tailored for processing LiDAR data is crucial for ensuring smooth integration and optimal performance.

In essence, while the integration of LiDAR tools into GIS software offers significant benefits, overcoming challenges related to data volume, storage, management, and computational efficiency remains critical for seamless functionality.

Let's revise the same procedure in a focused software;

The LAS file is opened using a straightforward "Open LAS" command:

Fig.16 The same LAS file opened in SGIS Desktop vR

In the element data panel located in the upper right corner of the user interface, there is a LiDAR tool. Activating it opens a new window featuring a classifications panel with tools to manage them.

To remove the default list and preview only the actual existing classifications, we'll use the 'Uncheck Non-Existing Classifications' function.

This one-click function automatically unchecks all classifications not contained in the file, leaving only the existing ones.

Fig.17 Clicking the LIDAR data button brings up the LIDAR data management toolbox.

Here's how the toolbox appears when you select the 'Tools' tab:

Fig.18 Inside the 'Tools' tab, there's a list of tools where users can find the 'Uncheck Non-Existing Classifications' function.

The 'Uncheck Non-Existing Classifications' tool enables users to select or deselect multiple checkboxes with a single click. This feature eliminates the need for users to manually uncheck each checkbox individually. While users still have the option to manually manage checkboxes, this tool provides a convenient way to expedite data processing tasks, especially when speed is essential.

Fig.19 Displaying the seven active classifications, with the others removed.

In the tools tab, you'll find additional functions that are quite useful. The first tool is 'Get Existing Classification Numbers,' and the third on the list is 'Selection By Checked Classification.' These tools are designed to streamline user's workflow.

When you click on 'Get Existing Classification Numbers,' it retrieves and displays the classification numbers in a panel box, each representing a specific type of data, such as unclassified points, ground points, or buildings. Users can then select any classification number from the panel and use the 'Selection By Checked Classification' tool. This will highlight all points of the chosen classification in the graphics panel.

Fig.20 Classification number 2 representing ground points is selected from the toolbox and displayed in the graphics panel

Fig.21 Ground points isolated into new GIS layer for further processing

Since the graphics panel is interconnected, we can easily use the 'Selection in a New Layer' function to isolate ground points or any other classification from the LAS file into a new GIS layer. The new layer will automatically appear in the layers panel list, allowing us to export it as a separate file, create a grid layer, generate a DEM, or save it as a text file. This toolset significantly simplifies the process of managing and manipulating LiDAR data.

So, to effectively manage LIDAR data, a GIS platform should:

- Handle large datasets without performance issues.
- Support LIDAR data formats to avoid time-consuming conversions.
- Manage high-resolution data smoothly without lag.
- Require technical expertise in both LIDAR and GIS technologies for developers and users to manipulate data correctly and implement the appropriate code effectively.

We will now create a comparison table to showcase the efficiency of both GIS software for this specific task, and how this relates to the principles of Green Information Technology development:

Criteria	QGIS	SGIS Desktop	Impact on Green Information Technology
Dataset Handling	Struggles with very large datasets; performance may degrade	Efficient handling of large datasets without compromising performance	SGIS reduces computational overhead, promoting energy efficiency
LIDAR Support	Requires external plug-ins (e.g., LASTools); some tools need licensing	Built-in tools specifically designed for LIDAR data management	Integrated tools in SGIS reduce the need for additional installations, saving resources
High-Resolution	Can experience lag with high-resolution data	Smooth handling of high-resolution data	SGIS's efficient data processing minimizes energy

Data		without significant lag	consumption
User Expertise Required	Users need to install and manage plug-ins; requires technical knowledge for optimal use	More user-friendly with intuitive tools and minimal additional installations	SGIS's ease of use reduces time and energy spent on training and troubleshooting
Classification Management	Manual unchecking of non-existing classifications required	Automatic unchecking of non-existing classifications	SGIS streamlines the workflow, reducing the time and energy required for data management
Workflow Efficiency	Additional steps needed for installing and managing plug-ins	Built-in tools for streamlined workflow	SGIS's efficiency directly correlates with lower energy use and faster task completion
Export and Integration	Requires additional steps to isolate and export classifications	Direct export to new GIS layers	SGIS's integrated export options minimize the need for external tools, conserving energy

Task # 3 – Colorize LAS

The third task in our research involves colorizing a LAS file. This means assigning RGB values from imagery to overlaying LAS points.

Fig.22 A LAS point cloud from a semi-urban area near Skopje, North Macedonia. The left image shows the point cloud opened in open-source software, while the right image displays the LAS point cloud with its RGB values, providing a clearer and more intuitive understanding of the environment.

What are RGB values?

RGB stands for Red, Green, and Blue, which are the primary colors in additive color synthesis.

An RGB file consists of composite layers of Red, Green, and Blue, each encoded on 256 levels ranging from 0 to 255. For example, black corresponds to R=0, G=0, B=0, and white corresponds to R=255, G=255, B=255. This RGB system is used by screens, scanners, and digital cameras.

The Math Behind RGB Values

In HTML, a color can be specified as an RGB value using the formula:

```
rgb(red, green, blue)
```

Each parameter (red, green, and blue) defines the intensity of the color with a value between 0 and 255. This means there are $256 \times 256 \times 256 = 16,777,216$ possible colors![\[51\]](#)
For example:

- `rgb(255, 0, 0)` displays as red because red is set to its highest value (255), while green and blue are set to 0.
- `rgb(0, 255, 0)` displays as green because green is set to its highest value (255), while red and blue are set to 0.

To display black, set all parameters to 0:

```
rgb(0, 0, 0)
```

To display white, set all parameters to 255:

```
rgb(255, 255, 255)
```

RGB is a color model used in graphics computing where colors are produced by emitting light rather than by absorbing it, as is the case with ink on paper. This model is commonly used for displaying images on monitors.

Why Colorize a Point Cloud?

Standard point clouds are incredibly useful, but colorizing them makes them even more valuable. Adding colors and near-infrared values from images to LAS points creates an immersive, photorealistic display. This enhanced visual feedback offers deeper insights into the characteristics of the point cloud, which is especially helpful for tasks like interactive data classification, digitizing new features, and setting reference points for 3D distance measurements.

Colorized point clouds are particularly beneficial in construction and engineering projects involving multiple stakeholders. For those who may not be experienced in reading plans or can't visit the site, a colorized point cloud provides helpful context and greater realism.

It is common to convert LIDAR point clouds to raster format for visualization, even though this can lead to some loss of detail. Pixels that represent more than one point will have a unique RGB value, which may not capture all the nuances of the original data. Despite this, the use of 'LAS to Raster' tools remains more popular than colorizing points clouds, even though colorized point clouds provide more clear and insightful visualizations.

- Colorizing Points with Imagery

Colorizing points means adding color information from raster images to point cloud data, like LiDAR. Since point cloud data typically lacks color, this process helps visualize the data in a broader context.

- **Colorizing LAS Files with GeoTile Map Images**

Often, a LiDAR LAS file doesn't fit neatly within the bounds of a single raster image. Usually, you need multiple raster images to cover the entire LAS file. One way to handle this is by merging all the raster images into one mosaic file. Alternatively, we can keep the raster images separate and load them one by one as needed to colorize the LAS file. And the third alternative is using a tile base as another option for certain cases.

As mentioned earlier, QGIS utilizes LASTools for processing LiDAR data, including rapidlasso's closed-source tool, lascolor, which is specifically used to apply color to LiDAR points based on imagery.

The lascolor tool allows the user to add color to LiDAR points using imagery, typically ortho-photos. Here's how it works and the options available:

Fig.23 lascolor tool shown in the 'Visualization and Colorization' tab of the LASTools plug-in

1. **Color Application:** According to the lascolor documentation, lascolor determines the corresponding pixel for each LAS point and assigns the appropriate RGB values. It currently supports only TIF format, with world coordinates provided via GeoTIFF tags or a *.tfw file (Isenburg, n.d.) .
2. **RGB Scaling:** By default, 8-bit RGB colors from the TIF file are upscaled to 16 bits to comply with LAS specifications. Use the `-dont_scale_rgb_up` option to avoid this upscaling.
3. **Handling Outliers:** LiDAR points outside the image or in no-data areas are not colored by default. Use the `-zero_rgb` option to set their color to (0/0/0).
4. **Custom Color Channels:**

- Copy a single color channel (-red, -green, or -blue) or a grayscale band (-grey) into all three RGB channels.
 - Specify which band to copy from with -band (default is band 0).
 - Copy Near-Infrared (NIR) data using -nir and specify the band with -band 3.
5. **RGB and NIR Copying:** With a 4-band RGBNIR input image, use -rgbnir to copy all bands into the RGB and NIR channels or into RGB and intensity fields with -intensity.
 6. **LAS 1.4 Requirement:** To store data in the NIR channel, the LAS file must be LAS 1.4. Use las2las to upgrade if necessary.
 7. **Batch Processing:** Process an entire folder of LAS/LAZ files with corresponding image files using -imagedir ortho instead of specifying a single image file. Omit both options if TIF files are in the same folder as LAS/LAZ files. Multi-core processing with -cores 4 can significantly speed up the process.
 8. **Classification Option:** Classify points based on the pixel they fall into using options like -classify_as 10, -classify_not_black, -classify_white, or -classify_not_white.

["Please license from martin@rapidlasso.com before using lascolor commercially. Please note that the unlicensed version will set intensity, gps_time, user data, and point source ID to zero, slightly change the LAS point order, and randomly add a tiny bit of white noise to the points coordinates once you exceed a certain number of points in the input file."][52] (Isenburg, n.d.).

Fig.24 The lascolor function initiated with input parameters specifying a LAS or LAZ file and an orthophoto in TIF format.

Now, let's compare it with SGIS's algorithm;
Let's begin by importing the LAS file into the SGIS software:

Fig.25 A LiDAR point cloud and a tile-based map displayed in SGIS Desktop vR.

Previously, we incorporated Google Satellite Imagery as a background layer. The algorithm seamlessly integrates with both image layers and tile map service layers. To showcase its efficiency and speed, we will colorize the LAS file using the base tile map as the underlying backdrop.

Fig.26 The 'Colorize LAS' function colorizes lidar data through raster overlay.

We need to proceed to the 'Colorize LAS' function. To access it, we simply click on it.

Fig.27 The dialog window for the 'Colorize LAS' function, allowing users to select their LAS layer and raster/TMS layer from the lists. Once selections are made, clicking 'Colorize' initiates the process.

Once the function is activated, a new dialog window appears. This window allows the user to select their LAS layer and their raster/TMS layer from the respective lists. After making these selections, we simply click on 'Colorize'.

Fig.28 The LAS point cloud colored in RGB.

Here's a comparison analysis table based on the efficiency of executing the colorization algorithm in both GIS software (QGIS with LASTools and SGIS Desktop) and its alignment with Green Software Development and Green IT principles:

Criteria	QGIS with LASTools (lascolor)	SGIS Desktop (Colorize LAS)
Algorithm Execution Efficiency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Speed: Relatively fast but depends on system resources. ▪ Input Requirements: Requires LAS/LAZ files and orthophotos in TIF format. ▪ Integration: Uses the closed-source lascolor tool from rapidlasso. ▪ Usability: User must manage multiple files and settings; the process can be complex for new users. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Speed: Optimized for fast performance, even with large datasets. ▪ Input Requirements: Supports both image layers and tile map service layers. ▪ Integration: A new algorithm independent of rapilasso, integrated directly into SGIS Desktop, providing a seamless workflow. ▪ Usability: Intuitive interface with straightforward options, suitable for both new and experienced users.
Green Software Development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Resource Efficiency: Efficient but may require significant system resources for large datasets. ▪ Energy Consumption: Can be high due to the processing power needed for lascolor operations. ▪ Optimization: Limited optimization for energy savings in lascolor tool. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Resource Efficiency: Designed to be resource-efficient, reducing system load. ▪ Energy Consumption: Lower energy consumption due to optimized algorithms. ▪ Optimization: Focus on minimizing energy use and maximizing processing efficiency.
Green IT Alignment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Environmental Impact: Potentially higher due to increased resource and energy use. ▪ Sustainability Practices: Limited focus on reducing CO2 emissions within the lascolor tool. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Environmental Impact: Lower due to efficient processing and reduced energy consumption. ▪ Sustainability Practices: Emphasis on sustainable software development practices, aligning with Green IT principles.

Fig.29 Comparison table evaluating the efficiency of the colorization algorithm execution in GIS software (QGIS with LASTools vs. SGIS Desktop) and its alignment with Green Software Development and Green IT principles.

Task #4 - Cadastral Data Integration for Urban Planning: Utilizing UAV-Sourced Orthophotos and Point Cloud Data

In North Macedonia, the Republic's Agency for Real Estate Cadastre maintains precise building data, crucial for urban planners undertaking various projects. Since 2012, the Agency has officially operated with GIS data, providing digital cadastral plans covering the entire country, available for professional purchase.

Building footprints can be extracted effortlessly from these plans. However, these resources primarily consist of vector data distributed as GIS zip archives containing SHP files rich in polygonal data with associated attributes. In urban planning projects, overlaying these building polygons with current point cloud and orthophoto data is essential for extracting diverse information. Our recent research focused on validating property boundaries and cadastral parcels against real-world conditions.

These outlines include vital legal details about parcel and building associations, along with land-related rights, restrictions, and obligations. Accurate data is crucial for urban planners, particularly in areas like Struga municipality's Radozda village, renowned for its cultural heritage and tourism significance.

We conducted a thorough assessment of existing buildings in our database using point cloud models, orthophoto maps, and supplementary materials. Our objective was to enhance the accuracy and currency of the housing database, ensuring high-quality information for the users. This included correcting building geometries as necessary and adding new buildings that were previously absent. Additionally, we updated and improved attribute information associated with these buildings. Among various methods available, the quickest and most effective approach involved utilizing drones for data capture and UAV data manipulation. Drones were employed extensively in this operation to ensure precision and efficiency.

Integrating drones with GIS significantly lowers costs and enhances the accessibility of geospatial data collection (Quamar et al., 2023).

Effectively using GIS throughout every step of the procedure is crucial, as it enriches the final GIS data with detailed attribute information. Avoiding the hassle of switching between two different platforms—one for processing point cloud data and another for GIS—was a significant efficiency boost worth exploring. This approach not only saves valuable time and resources—both in terms of computing power and costs—but also simplifies the learning curve for users, who would otherwise need to master multiple tools. Starting with open-source QGIS, let's delve into what users can accomplish;

In our GIS project, we decided to examine the open-source 'Magic Wand' tool for this purpose, and compared it with other existing technology. This tool processes pixel data from images, enabling users to select areas based on color similarity within raster layers.

Such functionality is particularly valuable for tasks like image segmentation and pinpointing specific features within an image. Essentially, it identifies clusters of pixels that collectively form distinct objects ("Development of an outline detection tool," 2015).

Given our existing precise building outlines, our focus won't be researching on an algorithm capable of extracting vector outlines from raster data, but rather segmenting raster pixels image from orthophoto / true orthophoto images, based on color values.

This involves selecting areas of interest that exhibit color similarity, and segmenting those areas as separate layers for further analysis. We will assess the similarities and differences between these two algorithms based on their outcomes.

We mentioned Magic Wand, a plug-in tool used by QGIS for this purpose, which is implemented as such for several reasons:

- Firstly, the basic software design is modular, allowing users to extend its functionality through plug-ins. These types of plug-ins are developed independently, providing specialized functionalities that are not part of the core software. This independence also means that the tool can be updated and improved separately from the main QGIS software.
- Additionally, not all users need this functionality, so having the option not to install the plug-in keeps the software efficient and prevents bloating the core QGIS installation.

Let's first see what happens with Magic Wand:

Fig.30 An orthophoto loaded in QGIS with the Magic Wand tool activated.

When activating the Magic Wand plug-in, users can adjust two main parameters:

- Accuracy
- and Color Threshold.

Accuracy can be adjusted ranging from fast (least accurate) to precise (most accurate). The Color Threshold setting allows users to adjust from ambiguous to strict, determining the range of color values around the selected color that will be included in the selection.

With the Color Threshold adjusted to lean towards 'Ambiguous', this is the result:

Fig. 31: Result with Color Threshold set towards 'Ambiguous'.

There are several algorithms available to smooth edges and rectify outlines, but they lack the precision required for our task. The 'Magic Wand' tool is particularly appealing because it automatically selects and groups pixels that are similar in color and spatially connected, starting from a seed pixel (Development of an Outline Detection Tool, 2015). Many general library algorithms exist for this purpose, but their accuracy is yet to be fully validated. The Magic Wand tool performs well on objects with sharp edges. For instance, if a user selects an area with a solid color representing buildings, the tool effectively selects pixels based on the initial seed pixel from the image. This primary selected pixel serves as the seed, and all other pixels with sufficiently similar color values are included. This seed selection process continues until no more pixels can be added (Casciati, Casciati, Faravelli, & Vece, 2015).

However, for this task, we need somewhat different algorithm.

We need an algorithm that can spot groups of pixels forming distinct objects and then export them, or separate them into individual layer images. Our goal is to extract only the pixel clusters representing buildings so we can overlay and compare them with our existing building polygon footprints.

To achieve this, we used SGIS Technology: First, we loaded the raster file into the SGIS Raster Project. Once the TIF file is loaded, it appears in the 'Loaded Image Tab.' Using Control+Left Click, the user can select the desired color value. The selected color value will then appear in this square window box:

Fig. 32 A TIF raster file loaded into SGIS Raster Project

Fig. 33 After selecting the color value, the chosen color appears in the color box.

Once the desired color is displayed, the user can click on 'Show Color Threshold.' This one-click operation fills the boxes with similar colors, creating a seed palette. Next, the precision needs to be set using a numerical input, ranging from 500 to 65,000. In this example, it's set to 20,000.

After setting the precision, click on 'Execute.' The software then creates another layer that displays only those raster color values. Essentially, we obtain a building raster footprint that can be used as a backlayer alongside existing orthophoto images. This footprint takes up far

less storage space and can be easily implemented in batch processes or for checking larger areas, as it requires minimal resources.

Fig.34 The output is a raster image file containing the building footprints needed for the overlay. These image files take up much less storage space and are very useful in batch processing, especially for large projects covering extensive areas.

Fig. 35 Close-up view of Figure 34

Throughout all our research tasks, we keep mentioning the importance of aligning with Green IT and Green Software Development. What exactly does that mean?

In the context of all GIS tasks, aligning with Green IT and Green Software Development means:

- **Reduce Computational Complexity:** Energy-efficient algorithms focus on simplifying computational tasks. By minimizing time and space complexity, these algorithms require fewer resources and consume less energy during operation.
- **Optimize Memory Use:** Efficient data structures are smart about using memory. By keeping the memory footprint small and improving the way memory is accessed, these structures can significantly cut down the energy needed for memory operations like reading and writing. SGIS's technology, exemplified throughout all three tasks, is optimized for minimal storage usage. When using SGIS Desktop v1.0 with multiple data layers open, the system displays an allocated heap size of 146 MB, with 12 MB of free heap available. This information allows users to monitor memory usage and manage resources effectively within the software. For comparison, you can open your task manager to see how much storage a basic browser like Google Chrome consumes during use.
- **Minimizing Data Redundancy:** Reducing data redundancy and optimizing data storage solutions to lower the amount of storage required and the associated energy usage.
- **Leveraging Renewable Energy:** Where possible, using renewable energy sources to power the systems and data centers involved in processing GIS data.
- **Sustainable Practices in Software Design:** Designing the software to be energy-efficient, minimizing the need for frequent updates or upgrades, and ensuring compatibility with existing hardware to extend its lifespan.

Fig.36 When using SGIS Desktop v1.0, with multiple layers of data opened, the system displays an allocated heap size of 146 MB, with 12 MB of free heap available. This information helps users monitor memory usage and manage resources effectively within the software.

Fig.37 SGIS v1.0 displaying over 40 layers including point, polyline, and polygon data from three cadastral municipalities. The system manages a substantial 555MB allocated heap with 5MB free, showcasing efficient handling of complex geospatial datasets.

To thoroughly test SGIS v1.0 technology, we've loaded over 40 layers encompassing point, polyline, and polygon data from three different cadastral municipalities. These layers include parcels, buildings, municipal boundaries, building numbers, pavements, rivers, ortho-blocks, and more. Currently, the system displays an allocated heap of 555MB, with 5MB of free heap available. This test was performed on a computer with the following specifications: Intel i5-7200U CPU @ 2.50GHz, 2701 MHz, 2 cores, 4 logical processors, and 4GB RAM. This allocation of heap memory is substantial for GIS software, particularly when managing a large volume of diverse geospatial datasets. It demonstrates SGIS v1.0's efficiency in handling complex GIS data efficiently.

Why Algorithms Matter for Efficiency

Efficiency is crucial in programming, and developing smart algorithms is key to achieving it. Here's why algorithms are so important for optimizing performance:

Faster Execution: Good algorithms make programs run faster, allowing them to handle large amounts of data quickly.

Reduced Resource Consumption: Efficient algorithms use less memory, CPU power, and disk space, helping manage resources more effectively.

Improved Scalability: Well-crafted algorithms can handle increasing workloads, making software systems capable of growing and adapting to new demands.

Big Data Processing: In today's era of big data, efficient algorithms play a crucial role in processing and analyzing vast datasets. They empower businesses to extract valuable insights, enabling informed and data-driven decision-making.

Embracing Energy-Efficient Innovations

Tech leaders are pushing for lower power consumption in data centers, knowing it's crucial for sustainability. This focus has led to a big interest in creating algorithms that not only work well but also use less energy. These energy-efficient algorithms are key to handling growing computational needs while keeping the environmental impact of our digital infrastructure in check.

The Economic Advantages of Green IT

1. Cost Savings

- **Energy Efficiency:** Reducing energy consumption through efficient algorithms and resource optimization can significantly lower electricity costs, particularly in data centers and large-scale IT operations (The Renewables, n.d.).
- **Resource Utilization:** Efficient use of hardware and software resources can extend the life of existing equipment, reducing the need for frequent replacements and lowering capital expenditures.

2. Regulatory Compliance

- **Environmental Regulations:** Many countries have regulations in place that require businesses to reduce their carbon footprint. Aligning with Green IT practices helps businesses comply with these regulations and avoid potential fines or penalties.
- **Sustainability Reporting:** Increasingly, businesses are required to report on their sustainability efforts. Green IT and software development practices can provide positive metrics for these reports, enhancing the company's reputation.

3. Market Differentiation

- **Brand Image:** Companies that adopt green practices can enhance their brand image and reputation. Being known as an environmentally responsible business can attract customers, partners, and investors who prioritize sustainability.
- **Competitive Advantage:** Differentiating through sustainability can provide a competitive edge. Companies that demonstrate commitment to green practices can appeal to a growing segment of eco-conscious consumers and clients.

4. Customer Demand

- **Sustainable Products:** There is an increasing demand for products and services that are environmentally friendly. Businesses that offer green IT solutions can meet this demand and capture new market segments.
- **Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR):** Customers are more likely to support companies that take their CSR seriously, including efforts to minimize environmental impact. Green IT initiatives can enhance a company's CSR profile.

5. Innovation and Efficiency

- **Process Optimization:** Implementing green practices often leads to more efficient processes and innovations that can improve overall business operations.
- **Employee Engagement:** Engaging employees in green initiatives can boost morale and attract talent who are passionate about sustainability.

6. Risk Management

- **Supply Chain Resilience:** Sustainable practices can lead to a more resilient supply chain, less susceptible to disruptions from environmental factors or resource shortages.
- **Future-Proofing:** As global focus shifts towards sustainability, companies that are already aligned with green practices will be better positioned for future regulatory and market changes.

7. Investment Opportunities

- **Green Investments:** There is a growing pool of investors looking to fund environmentally responsible companies. Aligning with green practices can make a business more attractive to these investors.

Social Impact

Contribution to an Eco-Friendly Environment: Green IT practices help reduce the environmental impact of technology. Software developers play a crucial role in this by optimizing their applications' performance, leading to lower energy consumption. Simply put, better code means less energy use, benefiting the planet (VirtusLab, n.d.).

Encouraging a Culture of Sustainability: Many companies meet legal environmental requirements but often rely on selective data or offsets that don't truly cut their carbon footprint. By nurturing a culture of sustainability, you can inspire employees and stakeholders to adopt eco-friendly habits in their personal lives, creating a broader positive effect (Dang, Khan, Doan, & Ibbett, 2021).

Need for Experts in Their Field: As organizations prioritize energy efficiency and eco-friendly practices, there's a rising demand for professionals skilled in sustainable technology, green data management, and environmental compliance. This highlights the growing importance of expertise in these crucial areas.

Overcoming Challenges in Green IT Implementation

While Green IT offers numerous benefits, it also presents significant challenges. The path to sustainable IT practices is filled with obstacles that organizations must carefully navigate.

- **Software's Carbon Footprint:** Software significantly contributes to CO2 emissions, impacting the climate and increasing the likelihood of extreme weather events. The carbon footprint of the cloud, growing by 9% annually, now exceeds that of the airline industry.
- **Complexities of Digital Transformation:** Embracing digital transformation offers environmental benefits but introduces complexities. Each digital transaction requires energy, physical infrastructure, and devices, impacting resource usage from production to disposal.

Common Challenges Organizations Face [2]

One of the biggest challenges in adopting Green IT practices is the initial cost involved (VirtusLab, n.d.). Whether you're running a small business or a large corporation, tight budgets can make it tough to invest in sustainable technologies, even though they promise long-term benefits. A practical approach is to take small steps toward sustainability. What one can do is to start improving the current systems gradually while keeping existing

operations running smoothly. This might mean upgrading existing infrastructure, slowly moving to better technology, or refining your applications to integrate sustainability into your business strategy.

Another challenge is the **compatibility issues with existing infrastructure**. Legacy systems or outdated technologies can be hard to align with newer, sustainable solutions. This mismatch often leads to compatibility issues, necessitating extra time, resources, and sometimes a complete overhaul to ensure seamless integration, which can disrupt day-to-day operations. Many organizations opt to work with software engineering partners to swiftly and accurately implement tailored solutions. When selecting a partner, it's crucial to ensure they possess the expertise and experience needed to effectively update outdated systems

Resistance to change is a common obstacle when implementing Green IT initiatives. Employees and stakeholders often feel comfortable with existing systems, making them hesitant to adopt new, sustainable technologies. This reluctance can arise from fears of job loss, unfamiliarity with new systems, or doubts about the effectiveness of these changes. However, change can be positive when implemented with the end user in mind. A great leader should guide their team to success by collaborating closely with employees, addressing their concerns, and crafting solutions that benefit everyone inside an organization.

Sometimes, a **lack of awareness and understanding of sustainable practices** can pose a challenge. Vague sustainability laws often leave room for interpretation, reducing their effectiveness. Additionally, limited knowledge on how to implement these practices and improve organization's technology can hinder progress. Educating teams on sustainable methods and providing clear guidelines can bridge this gap, driving both environmental and technological advancements.

Conclusion

What is The Role of Energy-Efficient Algorithms in GIS?

Energy-efficient algorithms play a vital role in GIS, especially in supporting sustainable energy initiatives like the European Commission's "20–20–20" targets through initiatives such as the Sustainable Energy Action Plan (SEAP). These plans emphasize efficient energy management and quality control, where GIS provides essential data on building energy performance and consumption.

In urban contexts, GIS, coupled with technologies such as BIM, LIDAR, and Remote Sensing, aids in implementing and monitoring energy policies at regional levels. This integration supports policy-making and enhances urban planning and resource management.

However, behind these technological advancements lies ongoing development. Through this research, we emphasize the importance of refining algorithms and practices to promote green software development. This approach drives innovation in IT while contributing to a sustainable future. Examples in GIS, alongside LIDAR technology, demonstrate significant potential to achieve environmental goals and enhance efficiency.

Fig.31 A flowchart representing the implemented research about the topic of Green IT, the role of efficient algorithms in GIS as part of the big data community, and its implications

The efficiency provided by algorithms in problem-solving is a key factor that greatly enhances productivity across various domains. The right algorithm can simplify a complex problem, requiring minimal resources and time, which is highly valuable today. Throughout our research, we have emphasized that algorithms boost efficiency by optimizing resource use. Computationally, this means reducing the memory or processing power needed to solve a problem. However, their importance extends beyond this. The right algorithm can

significantly cut the time needed to find a solution, and we all know how critical time can be in determining success or failure.

While we have highlighted the importance of energy savings in this digital era, we must also consider the human effort and time that can be used more efficiently. In GIS technology and similar industries that handle vast amounts of data, effective algorithms that automate routine and repetitive tasks while promoting sustainability are invaluable. This allows human workers to focus on more complex and creative aspects of their work.

Moreover, developing algorithms that promote Green IT fosters creativity. Since there are often multiple ways to solve a problem, creative developers are encouraged to develop solutions independently rather than relying on external libraries. This creative problem-solving skill is particularly important in software development. By encouraging this approach, we promote innovative solutions that can lead to breakthroughs in both technology and user experience.

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